

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 0.98

A STUDY ON BEHAVIOR OF MUTUAL FUND INVESTORS IN INDIA

***Godala. Satya Narayana Reddy**

*Associate Professor,
ST.MARY'S ENGINEERING COLLEGE

ABSTRACT

Today a lot of investment opportunities are available to the investors in the financial markets. Investors can invest in corporate bonds, debentures, bank deposits, post office schemes etc. But nowadays investors opt for portfolio managers to invest money on their behalf. These portfolio managers are experts in stock market operations and invest the money in such a way that the investors would get minimum assured returns. Today many institutions are busy in providing wealth management services to the investors. But these services are very costly. Thus in order to help the investor's mutual funds provide a protective shed to the small and big investors. Indian mutual fund has gained a lot of popularity from the past few years. Earlier only UTI enjoyed the monopoly in this industry but with the passage of time many new players entered the market, due to which the UTI monopoly breaks down and the industry faces a severe competition. As the time passes this industry has become a buzz word in the Indian financial system. So it is very important to know the investors' perception about this industry. The present study analyses the mutual fund investments in relation to investor's behavior. Investors' opinion and perception has been studied relating to various issues like type of mutual fund scheme, main objective behind investing in mutual fund scheme, role of financial advisors and brokers, investors' opinion relating to factors that attract them to invest in mutual funds, sources of information, deficiencies in the services provided by the mutual fund managers, challenges before the Indian mutual fund industry etc.

Keywords: *Mutual fund, investors' perception, investors' behavior, objectives, challenges.*

Introduction

From its inception the growth of mutual funds is very slow and it took really long years to evolve the modern day mutual funds. Mutual Funds emerged for the first time in Netherlands in the 18th century and then got introduced to Switzerland, Scotland and then to United States in the 19th century. The main motive behind mutual fund investments is to deliver a form of diversified investment solution. Over the years the idea developed and people received more and more choices of diversified investment portfolio through the mutual funds. In India, the mutual fund concept emerged in 1960. The credit goes to UTI for introducing the first mutual fund in India. Monetary Funds benefited a lot from the mutual funds. Earlier investors used to invest directly in the stock market and many times suffered from loss due to wrong speculation. But with the coming up of mutual funds, which were handled by efficient fund managers, the investment risks were lowered by a great extent. The diversified investment structure of mutual funds and diversified risk contributed tremendously in the growth of mutual funds. With the passage of time many new mutual funds emerged. Not only this, the methods and ways of selling these funds also changed with time. But, the growth of mutual funds has not stopped. It is continuing to evolve to a better future, where the investors will get newer opportunities.

In this era of globalization and competition, the success of an industry is determined by the market performance of its stock. The investors too like to invest only in the stock of those companies from which they can get maximum gains. In early years of growth of mutual fund industry, investors were available only with few investment avenues to invest their money. But with the passage of time a lot of opportunities are available to the investors for investing their money in different investment channels.

The currently common mode of community investments, mutual funds have taken time in coming to India, while these have been a dominant feature for the last several years in the investment markets in the west and in the country of their origin, in USA they have become as ancient as money itself. Their slow coming into the country is due essentially to the Unit Trust of India having dominated the scene as the only institution of its kind all this time. After two decades of UTI monopoly some public sector organizations like LIC (1989), GIC (1991), SBI (1987), Can Bank (1987), and India Bank (1990) have been permitted to set up mutual funds.

2. Objectives of the Study

The Indian mutual fund industry is a very large industry consisting of number of investors. In this era of competition different investor's have different investment objectives. As the human behavior is unpredictable, this study helps in finding out the necessary facts regarding investors' opinion and perceptions regarding mutual fund investment. The main objectives of the study are:

1. To study the growth of mutual fund industry in India.
2. To analyze the investors awareness and perception regarding investing in mutual funds.
3. To find out the investors opinion regarding major deficiencies in the working of the mutual fund industry
4. To find out the suggestions from the investors that can help in plugging out these deficiencies.

3. Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is to track out the investors' preferences, priorities and their awareness towards different mutual fund schemes. Keeping in view the various constraints the scope of the study is limited only to the investors residing in Andhra Pradesh. Data for the study is collected from a sample of 200 investors by using stratified sampling. Out of all the questionnaires 196 questionnaires are considered valid for the purpose of the study.

4. Data Collection and Methods

For the purpose of the study two sets of data has been used. The first set of data is the primary data. This type of data has been collected from the investors with the help of a Questionnaire. The second set of data used for the study is the secondary data. The secondary data relating to net resources mobilized by banks and financial institution sponsored mutual funds, assets under management, investors mix etc is collected for a period of 2003-2010. This type of data is collected from different investment periodicals, magazines, various newspapers, RBI reports, AMFI reports, SEBI annual reports; securities market reviews, study of existing literature of different authors in the related field etc.

5. Statistical Tools Used

To carry out the research work different statistical tools are used in order to derive certain meaningful information and results. In case of primary data Chi Square tests has been applied and in case of categories where respondents are required to provide ranks to different factors, the relative importance of the respective factor is calculated by assigning scores to them. In case of secondary data exponential growth rates has been calculated.

6. Main Objective Behind Investing In Mutual Funds

Every investor has one or more objectives behind their investments in mutual funds. Without any investment objective, the investment is considered as useless. According to table 1 the main objective of the respondents behind investing in mutual funds is the tax benefits offered by it followed by high return and safety of the schemes. Therefore getting tax benefits from the scheme is the main motive of the

investors behind their investment in mutual funds.

Table 1

Ranking and scoring of factors considered by investors while investing in mutual funds

Factors	Ranks and Scores								Total F(S)	Ranks
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
Expertise	5 (40)	5 (35)	10 (54)	15 (75)	13 (52)	27 (81)	53 (106)	68 (68)	196 (511)	8
Safety	43 (344)	34 (238)	15 (90)	14 (70)	32 (128)	20 (60)	25 (50)	13 (13)	196 (993)	3
Liquidity	32 (256)	31 (212)	21 (126)	20 (100)	27 (108)	29 (87)	22 (44)	14 (14)	196 (947)	4
Diversification	13 (104)	20 (140)	17 (102)	11 (55)	21 (84)	32 (96)	38 (76)	44 (44)	196 (701)	7
Tax benefit	48 (384)	41 (287)	43 (258)	25 (125)	18 (72)	13 (39)	4 (8)	4 (4)	196 (1177)	1
Regular income	10 (80)	25 (175)	38 (228)	41 (205)	29 (116)	28 (84)	15 (30)	10 (10)	196 (928)	5
Regular savings	9 (72)	18 (126)	25 (150)	42 (210)	23 (84)	30 (90)	24 (48)	25 (25)	196 (805)	6
High returns	38 (304)	22 (154)	28 (168)	29 (145)	34 (136)	15 (45)	14 (28)	16 (16)	196 (996)	2

6.1 Factors that can win back the investors confidence to invest in mutual funds

Gaining the confidence of the investors is very essential for successful working of the mutual fund industry. In order to strengthen the investor's confidence to invest in mutual funds they must be offered transparency in services, tax benefits, minimum assured returns, consistency in performance etc. The study reveals that on the basis of qualification, occupation and annual family income the main factors that can win back the investor's confidence to invest in mutual funds are the minimum assured returns (32.14%) followed by transparency (28.58%) and consistency (22.44%). Table 2 shows that the demographic factors like qualification, age and annual family income have no significant relation with the factors that win back the investors' confidence at 5% level of significance whereas the age of the respondents have significant relation with the factors that win back the investors' confidence.

6.2 Features that attract the investor's most while choosing a mutual fund scheme

A lot many features are available in different mutual fund schemes that attract the investors to invest in mutual funds. These features may be their past performance, past dividend record, stability of returns etc. From the ranks assigned by the investors, it is found that, the most important feature that attract the investors while choosing a mutual fund scheme is the past performance of the scheme and the stability of the scheme which is followed by the past dividend records, the portfolio of the scheme, entry/exit load and the fund managers name as exhibited by table 3.

Table 2: Factors that can win back the investors confidence

(Chi Square

results)

Demographic Factors	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	12	.554	Not sig
Age	12	.375	Not sig
Occupation	16	.038	Sig
Annual family income	12	.864	Not sig

Table 3 : Ranking and scoring of features that attracts the investors most while choosing a mutual fund

Features	Ranks and Scores						Total	Ranks
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Past performance	67	47	37	25	14	6	196	1
Fund managers	14	6	21	25	40	90	196	6
Portfolio	25	25	20	50	50	26	196	4
Past dividend	15	45	48	39	29	20	196	3
Entry/Exit load	15	35	27	30	43	46	196	5
Stability of returns	58	41	44	26	18	9	196	2

Note: S-Scores, Figures in parentheses () are scores

7. SOURCES OF INFORMATION

For good and efficient decision making investors rely on different sources of information. The sources may be newspaper, brokers, tax consultants etc. Keeping the investors up to date with the latest information is very essential, so that they should be aware of different happenings in the mutual fund industry. The study reveals that for majority of the respondents newspapers (23.97%) are the main source of information followed by brokers (22.96%), internet (22.96%), and tax consultants (17.86%) and friends/relatives (10.74%). Table 4 exhibits that based on the chi square tests all the demographic variables have no significant relationship at 5% level of significance with the respondent's sources of information on which they rely for adequate information.

Table 4: Sources of information (Chi Square Results)

Demographic	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	15	.761	Not sig
Age	14	.674	Not sig
Occupation	20	.463	Not sig
Annual family income	15	.681	Not sig

8. CHOOSING RIGHT TYPE OF MUTUAL FUND

A lot many factors are available that are considered by the investors before investing in mutual funds. These factors are like consistency, ability, stability etc. Returns from the funds have a great impact on the mind setup of the investors. It is found from the study that majority of respondents believes that the past performance (47.44%) of the scheme is considered as an important element while choosing right type of mutual fund scheme. After past performance the investors give importance to stability (29.59%), consistency (17.34%) and ability (5.63%). From table 5 it is clear that all the demographic factors like qualification, age, occupation and annual family income have no impact on the factors considered by the investors before choosing the right kind of fund at 5% level of significance.

Table 5: Factors considered at the time of choosing right type of mutual fund (Chi Square Results)

Demographic	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	9	.079	Not sig
Age	9	.242	Not sig
Occupation	12	.619	Not sig
Annual family income	9	.36	Not sig

9. CRITERIA FOR EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF MUTUAL FUNDS

Most of the investors evaluate the performance of mutual funds before making investment in them. For evaluating the performance of different mutual fund schemes, a number of methods are available. As per the study, majority of the respondents prefer absolute returns of the funds (42.10%) and funds return to returns on other similar schemes (22.10%) as a criteria for evaluating the performance of mutual funds schemes. The study also reveals that the least preferred criteria for evaluating the performance of any fund is the fund returns to market index returns (10%). The chi square values at 5% level of significance as shown in table 6 reveals that all the demographic variables have no significant relationship with the respondent's criteria for evaluating the performance of the mutual funds.

Table 6: Criteria for evaluating the performance of mutual funds (Chi Square Results)

Demographic	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	15	.740	Not sig
Age	15	.244	Not sig
Occupation	20	.450	Not sig
Annual family income	15	.936	Not sig

10. MAJOR DEFICIENCY IN THE SERVICES PROVIDED BY THE MUTUAL FUND MANAGER

Besides providing numerous benefits, mutual fund industry also faces a lot of criticism from the investors. This section discloses the various deficiencies associated with the services provided by the mutual fund managers. According to majority of respondents the major deficiency in the services provided by their mutual fund managers is the lack of transparency (35.41%) which is followed by lack of periodical statements (18.23%), lack of awareness (15.63%), risk exposure (15.11%) and high expenses and costs (5.20%). Table 7 brings out that on the basis of chi square value all the demographic variables of the respondent's have no significant relation with the major deficiency in the in the services provided by the fund manager.

Table 7: Major deficiency in the services provided by the mutual fund manager (Chi Square Results)

Demographic	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	15	.422	Not sig
Age	15	.479	Not sig
Occupation	20	463	Not sig
Annual family income	15	.289	Not sig

11. The Main Challenge Before Indian Mutual Fund Industry

With the change in Indian financial set up and increase in competition, Indian mutual fund industry faces a number of challenges. In the near future industry will face many challenges in order to attract more and more investors. From the analysis of the study it is revealed that on the basis of the qualification, age, occupation and annual income, majority of respondents believes that the main challenge before Indian mutual fund industry is providing minimum assured returns to the investors (34.87%). However, according to some of the respondents educating the investors (21.53%) and managing their interests (15.38%) also acts as a challenge before Indian mutual fund industry. Based on the chi square tests, it is clear that all the demographic factors of the respondents have no significant relationship with the main challenge before Indian mutual fund industry as shown in table 8.

Table 8: Main challenge before Indian mutual fund industry

(Chi Square Results)

Demographic	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	15	.549	Not sig
Age	15	.833	Not sig
Occupation	20	.453	Not sig
Annual family income	15	.871	Not sig

12. Main Objective Behind Investing In Systematic Investment Plan (Sip)

Nowadays investing through SIP is treated as a very fruitful route of making investment in mutual funds. SIP is a method of investing a fix sum regularly in the mutual funds. It is very similar to the regular saving schemes like recurring deposits. The study shows that a large proportion of the respondents is aware of the Systematic Investment Plan (SIP). Besides this for majority of investors the main objective behind investing in SIP (Systematic Investment Plan) is the regular investment (40.36%) of the funds followed by regular savings (38.01%). However the least preferred objective of the investors behind their investment in SIP is convenience (21.63%). This trend is seen in case of all the categories i.e. on the basis of age, qualification, occupation and annual family income of the respondents. According to table 9 the

chi square values shows insignificant relationship which means that all the demographic variables i.e. qualification, age, occupation and annual family income have no significant relationship with the respondent's main objective behind investing in SIP.

Table 9: Main objective behind investing in SIP (Chi Square Results)

Demographic	d.f	Chi Square value	Sig or Not Sig
Qualification	6	.229	Not sig
Age	6	.126	Not sig
Occupation	8	.535	Not sig
Annual family income	6	.128	Not sig

13. Suggestions

A special column has been provided in the questionnaire for suggestions from the investors. Many investors took keen interest in providing valuable suggestions. On the basis of the findings of the study the important suggestions are listed below:

- The periodical statements of mutual fund companies are considered as a very important source of information to the investors. So it is very essential that these periodical statements should contain all the relevant information in a compiled form and managers must ensure that these statements should reach the investors in time.
- Mostly a lay person doesn't have enough knowledge to invest in mutual funds. So they depend on the fund managers who are experts in managing efficient portfolios. The fund managers should be the person of integrity and financial experts. They should have clear cut knowledge of when to invest and in which securities to invest .They should mobilize the investor's savings in such a way that they can get maximum benefits out of them.
- Some investors suggested that the fund values of fund should be informed to the investors through SMS on fortnightly basis. This will help the investors in keeping themselves up to date with the latest information and latest NAV's of different funds.
- Steps should be taken to boost the confidence and morale of the investors. This can be done through appropriate communication and by educating investors to invest in mutual funds. Timely and right information should be provided to them by different communication modes so that they come to know about the latest trends in the market.

References

1. Aggarwal, N And Gupta, M (2007) "Performance Of Mutual Funds In India: An Empirical Study", *The Icfai Journal Of Applied Finance*, Vol.13, No.9, Pp.5-16.
2. Bansal, L.K (1996), "Mutual Funds Management and Working" Deep and Deep publications, New Delhi, pp 34-39.
3. Bharna, S (2007), "Myths Of Systematic Investment Plan", *Mutual Funds In India* (ed.by Dutta Abhijit), Wisdom Publications, New Delhi, pp.91-92.
4. Bodla, B S and Bishnoi, S (2008), "Emerging Trends of Mutual Funds in India: A Study across Category and type of schemes", *Journal of Indian Management and Strategy*, Vol.13, p-15.
5. Chandra, P (1995) "The Investment Game: How to Win?" Tata Mc Graw Hill, New Delhi